

ASSESSMENT OF CHANGES IN HEART RATE VARIABILITY INDICES OF STUDENTS AFTER COVID-19 LOCKDOWN: A COHORT STUDY

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Abstract.

Introduction: The objective of this study was to investigate the heart rate variability indicators of students who had contracted COVID-19 after performing physical activity. The aim was to uncover the potential cardiac complications and dysregulations of the autonomic nervous system.

Material and Method: We explored about 11 heart rate variability indicators and their changes immediately after a 5-minute physical activity performed by using Proteus pes 3320 bicycle odometer. Furthermore, we conducted electrocardiographic recording using variational pulsometry. Recording and the analysis of ECG were carried out on a computer using special programs “Cardio reg” and “Cardio prog”.

Results: The study revealed that the activity of the heart rhythm regulation indices among students infected by coronavirus was significantly elevated compared to the healthy controls ($p < 0.05$). After the physical activity, the Tension Index, VBI, VRI and LF/HF indicators characterizing the sympathetic tone of HRV regulation were increased, while the coefficient of cardiointervals variation decreased among infected group students. Moreover, the ECG recording showed that after physical activity, the disturbances of cardiac functioning changed, accompanied by tachycardia.

Conclusion: The findings of this study demonstrate that short-term physical activity contributed to the transition of cardiovascular system indicators from the adaptive stress zone to the tense zone, which is likely due to the negative impact of COVID-19 on the capabilities of both the cardiovascular and nervous systems. Therefore, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of changes in HRV in the context of post-COVID-19 cardiovascular dysfunction among young adults.

Key words. Heart rate variability, COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, post-COVID syndrome, electrocardiography.

Introduction.

SARS 2019 Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19), caused by coronavirus 2, is a pandemic that has led to considerable morbidity and death across the world. The clinical manifestation of COVID-19 could be specifically displayed in a wide spectrum and self-limiting [1]. Acute manifestations of COVID-19 were widely researched and published; however, long-term sequela of COVID-19 are unknown and still investigated [2,3]. While the virus mainly affects the respiratory system, it also causes acute myopericarditis, acute coronary syndrome, congestive heart failure, cardiogenic shock, and cardiac arrhythmias [4]. The host cell receptor for SARS CoV-2 is the biologically critical enzyme ACE2 (angiotensin-converting enzyme-2), which is generated by angiotensin 1-7 from ANG II (angiotensin II) in the intact human LV (left ventricle). The virus has an RBD

(receptor binding domain) spike that enables contacting the extracellular region of ACE2. The binding of the spike protein RBD (receptor binding domain) to ACE2 brings the virion into proximity with the host cell surface membrane and induces conformational changes in the RBD that initiate the process of membrane fusion [5-7]. Along with that, there is the release of inflammatory mediators known as cytokine storm that causes diffuse alveolar damage, resulting in ARDS (Acute respiratory distress syndrome) [8,9].

The SARS 2019 Coronavirus Disease, also known as COVID-19, is a pandemic that has caused significant illness and death worldwide. While acute symptoms of COVID-19 have been widely researched and published, the long-term effects of the disease are still being investigated. Although the virus primarily affects the respiratory system, it can also cause cardiac problems such as acute myopericarditis, acute coronary syndrome, congestive heart failure, cardiogenic shock, and cardiac arrhythmias. A rat coronavirus model has shown that neutrophils produce cytokines and chemokines in response to alveolar epithelial cell infection with SARS-CoV-2, resulting in an inflammatory response that contributes to lung injury. In patients with cardiovascular disease, increased circulating ACE2 activity predicts adverse cardiovascular outcomes in patients with heart failure, coronary artery disease, and aortic stenosis [10].

Post-COVID-19 cardiovascular dysautonomia (PCCD) is a common condition that can be caused by direct damage from the SARS-CoV2 virus, cytokine storm-mediated dysregulation of the autonomic nervous system (ANS), or immune-mediated dysregulation of the ANS. This condition can be diagnosed using 12-lead electrocardiography (ECG) by measuring the time between two successive heartbeats. Heart rate variability (HRV) is a useful measure of ANS activity and can be measured using pulse oximetry or other devices. HRV can also be used to assess the course of the disease. In patients with COVID-19, cardiac complications can range from arrhythmias to ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) mimics, thrombus formation, and fulminant myocarditis. However, the arrhythmic risk related to COVID-19 is still being evaluated [11].

To better understand the cardiac complications associated with COVID-19, we aimed to assess the heart rate variability of young patients infected with the virus over the past 1.5 years. Our primary focus was to evaluate the heart's adaptive capabilities under physical exertion. This evaluation could help us identify potential cardiac disorders and develop strategies for treating post-COVID-19 complications related to cardiac dysfunction. Our study specifically examined the integral, histogramical, and spectral indicators of heart rhythm regulation in students who had contracted COVID-19.

Methodology.

Forty-four female students aged 18-22 and with a mean age of 19.5 (SD = 1.09), from the Yerevan State University's Faculty of Biology were examined. Ten of them were not infected with COVID-19 and acted as the control group. The study group consisted of 34 students who had been infected with coronavirus in the last 1.5 years. The disease manifested in all treated students with various symptoms such as fever, cough, weakness, sweating, loss of smell and taste, nausea, vomiting, intestinal problems, muscle and joint pain, headaches, and in some cases pneumonia.

The portable device has been developed at the Laboratory of Integrative Biology of the Institute of Physiology after L. Orbeli. The indicators of HRV were assessed in both groups after a 5-minute physical load on a special exercise bicycle. In order to evaluate the functional capabilities of the cardiovascular system, ECG recording and analysis were carried out using the method of variational pulsometry after Baevsky [12]. For this purpose, a hardware-software complex was used, which combines a portable electrocardiograph of the model "Bio-Art 001" and a computer equipped with automatic ECG recording and heart rhythm variation pulse measurement analysis programs. Three 5-minute ECG segments were analyzed for students in each study group. Any student who was suspected of having any cardiac disorders or risks underwent Holter monitoring and was excluded from the study. The experimental design is represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of study design. All students from the control and study groups underwent a 5-minute bicycle load after which the ECG analysis has been performed for HRV assessment.

The control group was selected based on clinical, laboratory, and physical examination data to exclude COVID-19 disease, any risk for cardiac, pulmonary, or related diseases, and comorbidities. ECG study and analysis programs were made according to the standards of the European Association of Cardiologists and the North American Association of Electrophysiology and Arrhythmology. To assess the adequacy of the heart rate regulation processes, the HRV assessment parameters proposed by Bayevsky and Mikhailov [12,13] were used. The following indicators were selected and studied for HRV assessment: histographic indicators - coefficient of variation of the examined mass of cardiointervals (CV), R-R(s). integral indicators: autonomic balance index (ABI): $ABI = AMo/\Delta X$, to determine the ratio of sympathetic and parasympathetic regulation of the heart; autonomic rhythm index (ARI); ARI

$= 1 / (Mo * \Delta X)$ - to assess the autonomic balance (the smaller the ARI, the more the autonomic balance is shifted towards the predominance of parasympathetic regulation); regulation adequacy index (indicator of the adequacy of the processes of regulation (RAI) = AMo/Mo , - to identify the correspondence between the level of functioning of the sinus node and sympathetic activity; strain index (SI) = $AMo/(2\Delta X * Mo)$, reflects the degree of centralization of heart rate control, and spectral indicators; power of the spectrum in the high-frequency range (HF, %) (0.15-0.4 Hz), which is related to the breathing act and reflects the level of activity of the parasympathetic nervous system in the process of heart rhythm regulation; low frequency (LF, %) - spectrum power in the medium frequency range (0.04-0.15Hz), is related to the arterial pressure and expresses the degree of activity of the sympathetic tone of heart rhythm regulation (although it has a mixed sympatho-parasympathetic origin); total power of spectrum (TP, ms^2) and spectrum power in the low frequency range (VLF, %) - (0.003-0.04 Hz); ratio of LF-to-HF power (LF/HF).

Statistical analysis.

Statistical analysis of research data is presented by mean and deviations ($M \pm m$). The significance between studied groups was determined using Student's t-test (paired) and the significance was considered as $p < 0.05$.

Results.

A 5-minute pedometer workout (3rd degree of load) was accompanied by moderate changes in all heart rate measurements. This is probably related to reduced physical activity, which has become even more pronounced in the last years due to distance learning during pandemics. The changes in HRV indicators for healthy controls before and after 5min physical load are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Changes in HRV indicators of healthy students of the control group before and after 5 min physical activity.

HRV indicators	Before physical activity	After physical activity
R-R (s)	0.75 ± 0.06	0.61 ± 0.07
CV (%)	7.83 ± 0.85	6.17 ± 0.68***
SI	140.90 ± 17.59	218.40 ± 22.50***
RAI	89.81 ± 9.34	158.30 ± 14.21***
ABI	232.91 ± 29.8	299.40 ± 28.2**
ARI	4.72 ± 1.32	9.49 ± 2.11***
TP (ms^2)	2351.0 ± 335.4	1200.8 ± 112.4**
VLF%	22.55 ± 6.7	14.38 ± 3.90
HF%	33.02 ± 8.21	37.06 ± 9.02
LF%	45.0 ± 13.62	48.70 ± 14.02
LF/HF	1.46 ± 0.60	1.65 ± 0.71*

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

After bicycle load, moderate tension in the activity of the sympathetic mechanisms of processes regulating the heart rhythm was observed in healthy controls, which was expressed by an increase in SI by 55% ($p < 0.001$). Furthermore, it was accompanied by a significant increase in the levels of other markers of the sympathetic tone, ABI, RAI and ARI by 28.5%, 76.2% and 101.0% respectively. Following the physical activity

the TP has changed from $2351.0 \pm 335.4 \text{ms}^2$ to $1200.8 \pm 112.4 \text{ms}^2$ (49.0%, $p < 0.001$), which was accompanied by a decrease in the middle- and high-frequency waves in the total spectrum (HF) with a weak increase in power by 3.68% and 4.0%, respectively, and a decrease in the spectrum of low-frequency (VLF) waves by 8.2%. As a result, the LF/HF indicator was increased by 13.0%.

The analysis of the neurovegetative regulation indicators among the students from the studied group showed that the HRV indicators of accompanied by a high functional tension of the heart. The results are shown in Table 2. The increase of SI (by 190%, $p < 0.001$) along with the other indicators characterizing the high activity of the sympathetic tone, particularly RAI, ABI and ARI were increased by 94.1%, 123.3%, 124.3% respectively ($p < 0.01$) in the COVID-19 infected group, in contrary of control group.

Table 2. Changes in HRV indicators of students from experimental group before and after 5 min physical activity.

HRV indicators	Before physical activity	After physical activity
R-R (s)	0.60 ± 0.05	0.52 ± 0.04***
CV (%)	7.74 ± 0.30	5.26 ± 0.36***
SI	201.70 ± 77.31	586.10 ± 86.42***
RAI	105.70 ± 6.37	205.21 ± 11.61***
ABI	239.18 ± 28.1	534.2 ± 45.8***
ARI	5.39 ± 1.34	12.09 ± 4.09**
TP (ms ²)	2131.0 ± 305.0	618.82 ± 93.4***
VLF%	20.87 ± 6.7	32.21 ± 6.0
HF%	20.89 ± 3.26	15.96 ± 3.02
LF%	58.40 ± 6.69	50.15 ± 6.02
LF/HF	2.16 ± 0.80	4.25 ± 0.79*

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

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Discussion.

During the physical activity, the students of the studied groups were considered to have tachysystole, arrhythmia, and cardiac output disturbances. The analysis of the cardiograms, rhythmograms, histograms and scattergrams of the student from the control group is presented in Figure 2 (A, a-e). After the 5min physical load, the functional tension was expressed with activation of the cholinergic link of regulation, and the total effect of regulation was accompanied by tachycardia, moderate destruction of automation, and dysregulation of PNS activity.

This is probably because, in normal conditions, the heart rhythm and cardiac output intracardiac mechanisms usually work efficiently. However, in the post-infected period, the heart rhythm regulation function is disturbed due to damage to the central nervous system. Evidence of this consideration is the pronounced increase of SI, AMo, and IC, as well as the sympathetic/parasympathetic index and the spectrum of low-frequency waves in the process of heart rhythm regulation in the studied group of students. In the conditions of a strong signal flow from the central nervous system, the intracardiac homo- and heteromeric mechanisms of cardiac regulation are unable to cope with the increase in tension, and consequently

Figure 2. Fragments of the original recordings of a cardiogram (a), scattergram (b), rhythmogram (c), histogram (d), and spectrogram (e) of the student from the control group after a 5min bicycle load.

the imbalance in the frequency and strength of the heart contractions occurs. These changes cause the tension of vessel walls, arrhythmia, extrasystole, tachycardia, and other cardiac disorders. From Figure 2 it can be considered that in students from the healthy group, the vegetative homeostasis was preserved with sustainable regulation and normal activity of PNS.

While the student from the studied group was infected with coronavirus disease, there was observed a severe disturbance of automatism of the heart, tachycardia, and sinus arrhythmia. Although the vegetative homeostasis was preserved, the dysregulation with a predominance of subcortical nerve center activation and moderate weakening of the PNC activity has been recorded (Figure 3).

The severity of clinical manifestations of the heart depends on the degree of heart muscle damage. According to Mikhaylovskaya [14] elevated levels of troponin, myoglobin, C-reactive protein, serum ferritin, and interleukin-6 in deceased patients were revealed. This suggests the high inflammatory activity of COVID-19 and predicts an increase in cardiac lesions due to myocardial inflammation. Most likely, the coronavirus also has an effect on the students' organism that reduces muscle performance, helps to overcome physical load with the pronounced tension of the sympathetic systems, and increases the manifestation of sympathetic reactions, which is evidenced by the changes in the heart rate indicators that we observed. The effect of COVID-19 on lung tissue is weakened by the blockade of the renin-angiotensin system. This has been proven

by experiments on rats. Under the influence of COVID-19, a decrease in systemic pressure is observed, which leads to an increase in the activity of the renin-angiotensin system. This in turn, causes an increase in systolic blood pressure (SBP), leading to an increase in heart contractions frequency (HCF), tachysystole, and arrhythmia [15,16]. Disorders of the cardiovascular system were also observed in children, in the post-COVID period, the disease was also manifested in the form of Kawasaki syndrome. Most of them did not have serious respiratory problems, but doctors prescribed forced ventilation to improve heart function and blood circulation [17].

Based on this body of basic and applied HRV research, we wish to urgently propose using HRV monitoring as an element of a larger framework of truly personalized health. HRV screening, analysis, and feedback can be applied immediately to the present COVID-19 pandemic [18]. Cardiovascular implications of Sars-COV-2 infection have been widely documented and associated with poor prognosis, which can be worsened by underlying cardiovascular diseases [19]. Accumulating evidence indicates that COVID-19 patients are burdened by a higher risk of malignant ventricular arrhythmias, with a potential contributing role of repurposed antiviral therapies [20]. The studies of post-acute COVID-19 sequelae across the spectrum of care settings of acute infection are also lacking. Addressing this knowledge gap will inform post-acute COVID-19 care strategies [21].

SARS-CoV-2 can also affect the cardiac system directly. The virus has been shown to potentially cause myocarditis (inflammation of the heart muscle), arrhythmias, and other

Figure 3. Fragments of the original recordings of a cardiogram (a), scattergram (b), rhythmogram (c), histogram (d), and spectrogram (e) of the student from the studied group before (A) and after 5min bicycle load (B).

cardiovascular complications, which can contribute to changes in HRV. Myocardial inflammation or damage could lead to altered electrical conduction in the heart, thereby reducing the variability in the intervals between heartbeats. In addition, COVID-19 can exacerbate pre-existing cardiovascular conditions, further impacting HRV [22].

SARS-CoV-2 infection has also been shown to significantly affect the autonomic nervous system, both during the acute phase of infection and in post-viral recovery (often referred to as "long COVID"). The virus can directly affect the CNS, particularly the brainstem, which is critical in regulating autonomic functions like heart rate. SARS-CoV-2 may interact with the autonomic centers in the brain, either directly through viral entry into neurons or indirectly through inflammation (cytokine storms and immune responses). This interaction may lead to an imbalance between the sympathetic and parasympathetic systems, resulting in altered HRV [23].

Limited understanding of the pathological mechanisms underlying post-COVID syndrome represents a critical challenge to effectively testing and treating this syndrome. Injury to the autonomic nervous system (ANS) has recently been suggested to be responsible for many of the aforementioned manifestations and may be key in the pathogenesis of post-COVID syndrome [24]. Therefore, our study reveals the HRV variability changed among students with COVID-19 and elucidated by various cardiac complications in post-infected period.

To summarize, the negative impact of COVID-19 on HRV is due to several factors. While SARS-CoV-2 can influence the cardiac system—especially through conditions like arrhythmias, the main reason for reduced HRV seems to be the virus's effect on the autonomic nervous system. This includes both direct and indirect influences on the CNS and increased systemic inflammation. In our study, we highlighted the significance of HRV as a non-invasive biomarker for assessing autonomic function. This can help guide potential interventions aimed at restoring balance in the autonomic nervous system, particularly for patients experiencing long COVID-19.

Moreover, we suggest that controlled breathing exercises (such as paced breathing, slow deep breathing, or diaphragmatic breathing) could be effective in promoting parasympathetic nervous system activity and help mitigate symptoms associated with autonomic dysfunction during and after the acute phase of the infection. Also, for the patients recovering from COVID-19 who exhibit low HRV (indicating autonomic imbalance or stress), we recommend a gradual introduction of physical activity. Moderate aerobic exercise, such as walking or cycling, has been shown to improve HRV by enhancing cardiovascular health and autonomic regulation. This intervention can be tailored to the individual's recovery status, starting with low-intensity exercises and progressing as tolerated.

Conclusion.

This study supports our understanding of heart rate variability changes and cardiac dysfunction among young people infected by COVID-19, which is crucial for diagnosing the post-infected complication of coronavirus. Elucidating the mechanisms of the impact of COVID-19 on the cardiovascular system will make it possible to provide timely and correct complex medical care to young and elderly patients.

Conflict of interest.

Authors declare about not having financial and personal interests.

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REFERENCES

1. Tong X, Cheng A, Yuan X, et al. Characteristics of peripheral white blood cells in COVID-19 patients revealed by a retrospective cohort study. *BMC Infectious Diseases*. 2021;21:1236-1237.
2. Asarcikli L.D, Hayiroglu M, Osken A, et al. Heart rate variability and cardiac autonomic functions in post-COVID period. *Journal of Interventional Cardiac Electrophysiology*. 2022;63:715-716.
3. Bowe B, Xie Y, Al-Aly Z. Postacute sequelae of COVID-19 at 2 years. *Nature Medicine*. 2023;29:2347-2357.
4. Alqahtani M.S, Abbas M, Alsabaani A, et al. The Potential Impact of COVID-19 Virus on the Heart and the Circulatory System. *Infection and Drug Resistance*. 2022;15:1176-1177.
5. Chung M.K, Zidar D.A, Bristow M.R, et al. COVID-19 and Cardiovascular Disease From Bench to Bedside. *Circulation Research*. 2021;128:1214-1215.
6. Lu J, Sun P.D. High-affinity binding of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein enhances ACE2 carboxypeptidase activity. *J. Biol. Chem*. 2020;295:52:18579-18580.
7. Shang J, Wan Y, Luo Ch, et al. Cell entry mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2. *PNAS*. 2020;117:11727-11728.
8. Gajendra S. Spectrum of hematological changes in COVID-19. *Am J Blood Res*. 2022;12:44-45.
9. McKenna E, Wubben R, Isaza-Correa JM, et al. Neutrophils in COVID-19: Not Innocent Bystanders. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2022;13:1-2.
10. Zhu H, Zhang L, Ma Y, et al. The role of SARS-CoV-2 target ACE2 in cardiovascular diseases. *J Cell Mol Med*. 2021;25:1342-1343.
11. Shah B, Kunal S, Bansal A, et al. Heart rate variability as a marker of cardiovascular dysautonomia in post-COVID-19 syndrome using artificial intelligence. *Indian Pacing and Electrophysiology Journal*. 2022;22:71-71.
12. Baevsky R.M, Kirillov O.I, Klitskin S.Z. Mathematical analysis of changes in heart rate during stress. Moscow: Nauka. 1984:220-221.
13. Mikhailov V.M. Heart rate variability: experience of practical application of the method. Moscow, Ivanovo. 2002:26-39.
14. Mikhailovskaya T.V, Yakovleva N.D, Safronov M.A, et al. Potential impact of COVID-19 on the cardiovascular system. *Physical and rehabilitation medicine*. 2020;2:133-139.
15. Levi M, Beverley J. Hunt Thrombosis and coagulopathy in COVID-19: An illustrated review. *Research and Practice in Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. 2020;4:1-8.
16. Tignanelli C.J, Ingraham N.E, Sparks M.A, et al. Antihypertensiv drugs and risk of COVID-19? *Lancet Resp Med*. 2020;8:e30-e31.

17. Harris C.K, Hung Y.P, Nielsen G.P, et al. Bone Marrow and Peripheral Blood Findings in Patients Infected by SARS-CoV-2. *Am J Clin Pathol.* 2021;115:627-637.
18. Drury R.L, Jarczok M, Owens A, et al. Wireless Heart Rate Variability in Assessing Community COVID-19. *Frontiers in Neuroscience.* 2021;15:1-2.
19. Brunetti N.D, Polisen M, Bottalico I.F, et al. Safety and heart rate changes in COVID-19 patients treated with Remdesivir. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases.* 2021;112:254-257.
20. Lazzerini P.E, Laghi-Pasini F, Acampa M, et al. IL-6 (Interleukin 6) Blockade and Heart Rate Corrected QT Interval Prolongation in COVID-19. *Circ Arrhythm Electrophysiol.* 2020;13:e008791.
21. Xie Y, Xu E, Bowe B, et al. Long-term cardiovascular outcomes of COVID-19. *Nature Medicine.* 2022;28:583-584.
22. Yugar-Toledo J, Yugar L, Sedenho-Prado L, et al. Pathophysiological effects of SARS-CoV-2 infection on the cardiovascular system and its clinical manifestations—a mini review. *Front Cardiovasc Med.* 2023;10:1162837.
23. Wei Zhuang-Yao, Liang K, Shetty A. Complications of COVID-19 on the Central Nervous System: Mechanisms and Potential Treatment for Easing Long COVID, *Aging Dis.* 2023;14:1492-1494.
24. Aranyó J, Bazan V, Lladós G, et al. Inappropriate sinus tachycardia in post-COVID-19 syndrome. *Scientific Reports.* 2022;12:298-299.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Оценка изменений показателей variability сердечного ритма у студентов после карантина COVID-19: когортное исследование

Введение: Целью данного исследования было изучение показателей variability сердечного ритма у студентов, переболевших COVID-19, после выполнения физической нагрузки. Целью было выявление любых потенциальных кардиологических осложнений и нарушений регуляции автономной нервной системы.

Материал и методы: Variability сердечного ритма и его изменения анализировались сразу после 5-минутной физической нагрузки, выполненной с использованием велоэргометра Proteus pes 3320. Регистрация и анализ ЭКГ осуществлялись на персональном компьютере с помощью специальных программ <<Cardio reg>> и <<Cardio prog>>.

Результаты: Анализ полученных данных показал, что активность показателей регуляции сердечного ритма у студентов, инфицированных коронавирусом, была значительно повышена по сравнению со здоровыми лицами ($p < 0.05$). После физической нагрузки у студентов инфицированной группы увеличились показатели индекса напряжения, VBI, VRI и LF/HF, характеризующие симпатический тонус регуляции ВСР, понизился коэффициент вариации кардиоинтервалов. Последнее сопровождалось тахисистолией и аритмией.

Заключение: Результаты этого исследования демонстрируют, что временные физические нагрузки способствовали переходу показателей сердечно-сосудистой системы из состояния адаптивного напряжения в состояние напряжения, что, вероятно, связано с негативным воздействием COVID-19 на функции как сердечно-сосудистой, так и нервной системы. Таким образом, исследование помогает лучше понять изменения variability сердечного ритма в контексте постковидной дисфункции сердечно-сосудистой системы у молодежи.